

SUBORDINATE CLAUSES AS A CLOSING ELEMENT OF DIALOGICAL UNITY (IN MODERN GERMAN LANGUAGE)

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Abstract. *The specificity of the isolation of parceled subordinate clauses is in many ways more clearly revealed when analyzing different types of parcels within the framework of the so-called dialogic unity. This term in the modern theory of stylistic syntax is understood as a structural-semantic unit of dialogical speech. As is known, dialogic speech is characteristic of oral speech in general (for example, the oral variety of literary language, etc.). For dialogical speech, it is primarily indicative of the absence of a pre-thought-out speech organization. And this leads to a certain incompleteness of its linguistic expression, which, as a rule, is compensated by the entire situation (as well as by other means, for example, facial expressions, gestures, etc.).*

Keywords: *pre-thought-out speech organization, prerequisites, dialogic unity, parcel, facial expressions, gestures.*

Studying the peculiarities of the use of parceled subordinate clauses in the language of fiction would be unthinkable without identifying the place of parcels in the structure of dialogic unity as the main unit of the dialogical form of speech. As is known, in the language of fiction, the dialogic form of speech (along with monologue) performs a special aesthetic function: the writer organizes a monologue and dialogue based on the main task of a work of art to have an aesthetic impact on the reader. The structure of dialogical unity has a specific character. To get a complete picture of such a structure, the following example is analyzed. In this example, the main sentence in the structure of the replica is not indicated, although it is assumed. If we construct this example differently, then the structure of the above dialogic unity will look different:

-Und was hast du ihnen gesagt?

-Ich habe gesagt, dass dein Brief ist.

If the structure of dialogic unity in the language of fiction had been built as we have built, then there would not have been any difficulty in clarifying the corresponding parcel type within the dialogical unity. However, the structural feature of dialogic unity makes it unnecessary to mention the main thing, i.e. in our case, the basic structure, since the situation presented is clear without it. The first replica in the above example acts as the base structure. The parcel, which is part of the dialogic unity, belongs to the first replica, structurally and semantically continuing it, with which the parcel forms a complex syntactic whole. Therefore, in our opinion, there is no doubt about considering the parcel as a closing or final element of any dialogic unity. The structure of dialogical unity is characterized by significant complexity: it can consist of two sentences (a remark and a response to it), three or more. They are united only by the necessary unity of structural semantic volume, which conveys the fullness of the information content necessary for a certain situation. As the analysis of examples drawn from modern fiction shows, the structure of dialogic unity becomes more complicated: it additionally includes all sorts of clarifying elements (they can be called as a connecting bridge between the parcel and the basic structure) in the replicas. However, as a rule, in such cases, the final position belongs to the parcel. At the same time, it is still necessary to take into account another feature of the use of parcels in the structure of dialogic

unity. It lies in the fact that, although the parcel is used at the end of the dialogic unity, it does not refer to the clarifying elements made in other remarks, but also to the basic structure. Consider the example below:

-Ich trinke nichts.

-Was?, Warum nicht?

-Weil ich keine Lust zu verdammten Sauferei mehr habe. (Remarque E.M. Drei Kameraden).

In the example given, the question words “was” and “warum” act as a clarifying element, moreover, with the negation “nicht”. The parcel “*Weil ich keine Lust zu dieser verdammten Sauferei mehr habe*” which follows the qualifying elements belongs to the so-called basic structure. The main function of these clarifying components is that they create the prerequisites for the use of the parcel as the final element of dialogic unity. The interrogative words “was” and “warum” require the use of some element that would contribute to the completion of the structure of dialogic unity. Such an element is always a parcel. The scope of dialogic unity is expanding. It includes not only individual question words, but also entire sentences, for example:

-Jetzt begreife ich dich endlich!

-Was begreifst du?

-Dass du die schlechten Rädchen beseitigen willst. (Werner Stein berg. Als die Uhren stehenblieb).

In this case, the interrogative sentence “*Was begreifst du?*”, acting as a connecting bridge between the parcel “*dass du die schlechten Rädchen beseitigen willst*” and the basic structure “*Jetzt begreife ich dich endlich*” creates the opportunity to complete the structure of this dialogic unity. Analyzing the structural feature of dialogic unity, we can note the following: as the factual material shows, not only the volume of dialogic unity itself is expanding, but also the basic structure itself, for example:

-Es gab eine Zeit, da konnte ich gar nicht erwarten, hier herauszukommen.

-Wenn denn?

-Als ich krank war. (Remarque E.M. Drei Kameraden).

In this example, the parcel “*Als ich krank war*” belongs only to the first part of the basic structure, i.e. “*es gab eine Zeit*”, and the rest of the basic structure “*da konnte ich gar nicht erwarten, hier herauszukommen*” acts as an explanatory element of the first part of the basic structure. The interrogative word “*wenn*” with the modal-evaluative element “*denn*” also requires a parcel as an answer. Based on the above material, the following preliminary conclusions can be drawn:

a) the structural features of dialogical unity are very diverse and the parcel acts as the closing element of dialogic unity;

b) a more detailed study of the structure of dialogical unity makes it possible to identify other patterns in the use of clarifying components between the parcel and the basic structure. Particularly in some cases for example:

-Ich habe mich sehr über dich gefreut, Carl", begann der alte Hardekopf.

-Wieso denn, Schwiegervater?

-Weil du das Politische so energisch betont und durchgesetzt hast. (W.Bredel Die Väter).

If we do not take into account in the composition of the dialogical unity, the so-called all possible clarifying components, like ..., “*begann der alte Hardekopf*”. “*Wieso denn Schwiegervater?*”, rearranging this statement as follows:

“*Ich habe mich sehr über dich gefreut, Carl Weil du das Politische so energisch betont und durchgesetzt hast*”

a) Can be considered not as dialogic speech, but as monologue speech;

b) of particular interest is the consideration of the parcel as the closing element of dialogic unity in stylistic terms, since the parcel takes an active part in the transmission of stylistic and semantic features of dialogic speech.

Here the parcel acts as a closing link in the dialogical unity of any structural organization. The need for such a transfer of the parcel to the culmination point of dialogic unity is caused by the logical-semantic feature of the dialogic constructions themselves, which involve the inclusion of the final part of the most important semantic-stylistic information. Such a summarizing function is performed by the parcel in the structure of dialogic unity, which will become the subject of our further research.

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